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Z OBSAHU
AUS DEM INHALT**

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Československé a maďarské vojenské zvyky na príklade Horných Salíb,
obce na Matúšovej zemi
Tschechoslowakische und ungarische Soldatenbräuche am Beispiel von Felsőszeli
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The Experience of Pandemic Time in Late Capitalism*

The Experience of Late Capitalist Temporality During the COVID-19 Pandemic: The Example of Poland

CELINA STRZELECKA

The Experience of Pandemic Time in Late Capitalism

The Experience of Late Capitalist Temporality During the COVID-19 Pandemic: The example of Poland

Abstract

The subject of this article is the transformation of social time in pandemic reality using the example of Poland. The situation caused by COVID-19 provided a unique opportunity to observe sudden changes in the social rhythm. This article which was conducted from the perspective of time studies, tries to specify what these changes are, additionally considering how social time was shaped in the economy of late capitalism. These observations show that changes in the organisation and experience of social time during the coronavirus pandemic were mainly shaped based on three categories: power, technology, and work.

Keywords: social time, pandemic time, power, technology, work, late capitalism.

The situation caused by COVID-19 has brought about various changes in the experience of time. Even though the basic assumptions of research on contemporary social time show the significance of many factors shaping it, I believe the most important ones among them are power, technology, and work. It is mainly from these elements that the current rhythms of late capitalism have developed. (Hassan 2009) I intend to demonstrate that their role has been instrumental in the transformation of time in the pandemic social reality. It is to these main factors (power, technology, and work) that the three subheadings of this article refer, organizing the structure of my argument: (1) the politics of pandemic time; (2) the impact of new technologies on the experience of time during the pandemic; (3) pandemic time and work.

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Observing the transformations in the experience of social time in Poland, during the first three months after the outbreak of the pandemic, I had casual conversations about the experience of changes caused by quarantine or isolation at home. I had already observed the life of the people I interviewed for this study half a year previously as part of a research project on cultural time management practices in neoliberalism. My interlocutors were residents of Poland's big cities with a population over 600,000. Moreover, considering the diffuse nature of the phenomenon of pandemic time, I cite various Internet materials in this paper that were produced in Polish in 2020. These include published newspaper articles and research papers, interviews, laws, recordings, blogs, and memes published on the Internet, commenting on the pandemic reality, and constituting immensely valuable evidence of the new temporal order. I analyzed the collected material in terms of power, technology, and work – the elements strongly influencing the form of social time in late capitalism. In Poland, these elements were also shaped by the context of the political transformation of the late 1980s and early 1990s, which effected a change in *governmentality*. (Dunn 2004)

The first case of coronavirus infection in Poland was officially reported on March 4, 2020. From that moment, the rate of transmission and the global spread of COVID-19 resulted in a great number of people spending weeks at home. This led to a sudden social change in how time was experienced. In less than a month, a chronobiological experiment on an unprecedented scale, impossible to arrange in controlled conditions, became reality. COVID-19, declared a pandemic by the WHO on March 11, proved to be an extraordinary opportunity to observe the transformations of social rhythm, which usually ensue as a slow process, difficult for researchers to study. The scope of this unplanned experiment is incomparable to the previous studies on time, such as the one Michel Siffre conducted on himself. In 1962, the French geologist spent 61 days deep in an icy Alpine cave in conditions of total isolation from all indicators and measures, as a result of which he lost count of and orientation in time¹. In a similar way, the COVID-19 pandemic and the related necessity of continuously staying at home threw people off their everyday experience in passing moments². The global scale of the pandemic experiment changing temporal rhythms is a social experience, which makes it an immensely interesting phenomenon from the perspective of studies on time (Fraser 1987; Adam 1995, 2008; Strang 2015) and the temporal turn (Hassan 2010) as well as from the perspective of the anthropology of time (Fabian 2002; Gell 1996; Munn 1992) and Polish sociology of time (Tarkowska 1987, 1992), with social time understood as a unique pattern of social behaviours and practices, produced by a community of experience, associated with the actions of individuals, groups, and social institutions. (Tarkowska 1987, 130)

The unplanned pandemic experiment caused a crisis of the usual perception of both individual and social dimensions of time, resulting in a reappraisal of the ideas and values related to time that seemed obvious, led to the defamiliarization of the previous understanding of what time was in social consciousness, increased uncertainty regarding the future, and generated questions about new conceptions of time and the outcomes of this transformation. In order to

1 For the entire duration of the experiment, Siffre was 130 metres underground and used a field telephone to communicate information about when he went to sleep, got up, and had meals and about how long he believed he had been in darkness. As a result, the geologist lost count of time because he was cut off from indicators and measures enabling orientation in time, such as sunrises and sunsets. Yet, despite the complete loss of the sense of time, a precise individual rhythm was established in his organism. The experimenter's day lasted 24,5 hours and his waking time was 16 hours. His biological time became his only measure of time, which he was not aware of until he was pulled out of the cave and acquainted with the results of the experiment.

2 Harmeeet Kaur (2020): The pandemic is messing with our concept of time. *CNN*, 28 April. Accessed: June 16, 2020. <https://edition.cnn.com/2020/04/28/health/what-day-is-it-pandemic-wellness-trnd/index.html>.

name and adapt in some way to the changes taking place, people started talking about “this strange,” “difficult,” “disturbing,” or “exceptional” time, which, along with its aspects of liminality and communality, took on the features of quasi-liminal time. (Turner 1969) In this transitional period, the social picture of the world began to take a new shape, and the ensuing transformations have resulted in previously unknown temporal divisions. There is no description of pandemic time that does full justice to its nature. Nobody knows what to call this time, and much less how to act in it. The present article does not aspire to give a homogeneous description of pandemic time; it merely outlines certain issues worth considering in the Polish context.

With the disorienting indeterminacy of pandemic time and with the consequences and problems associated with the loss of control over time, a phenomenon has arisen in Poland that can be called “the pandemic calendar.” Lists, registers, and charts appeared, filled with dates and numbers, which began to perform the function of bringing reality home; they establish specific coordinates facilitating navigation in the altered pandemic reality. Thoroughly constructed, supplemented with new data, and repeated by more and more information portals on a daily basis, the calculations satisfied the need of the human mind by providing coordinates that allowed people to identify and name their experiences³. Infection and mortality statistics were updated daily in Wikipedia on the basis of government sources. The data provided by the largest Internet encyclopedia, arranged chronologically along a timeline, molded human ideas into a structured picture of the situation. Charts, especially the incidence curve, visualized the evolution of the pandemic in time and thus constituted time themselves, attesting to the statistical regularity of infections. Reality began to be divided into the time before, during, and after the pandemic. Disrupting the previous flow of time, the COVID-19 pandemic proved to be an event so important that it became a kind of measure in the social system of reckoning time.

What attests to the significance of reflection on pandemic time is the fact that individual events, such as cataclysms, epidemics, floods, and fires, measured out the passage of time among specific communities in traditional societies. (Tarkowska 1992, 23) However, in the case of the coronavirus, the perception of time changed in all contemporary late capitalist societies, in which values such as openness to technology, work efficiency, freedom, and resourcefulness are promoted. As an observer of and participant in the sudden and significant changes in the organization of work and the organization of time during the spread of COVID-19, I shall try to specify what these changes consist of so as to better understand how social time has developed hitherto in the late capitalist economy and what purposes it has served.

The politics of pandemic time

According to Bram Ieven and Jan Overwijk, COVID-19 should be understood both literally and figuratively as a political actor, representing a mutation in the global policy of capital, which lead to a change in the capitalist and liberal rhythms of life⁴. The transformation of the experience of time has taken place as a result of the actions of public authorities, for whom control of time is a means of social superintendence. (Borowiec 2013) In order to manage the

3 For example, the Polish portal OKO.press published the following schedule: “On March 10, 6 days after (the first identified coronavirus case), all mass events were canceled; on March 12, 8 days after, schools and universities were closed; on March 15, 11 days after, a *cordon sanitaire* was established on the borders; on March 25, 21 days after, restrictions on contacts with people were imposed” (translation mine; Miłada Jędrzyk: Raport OKO.press. Jak rząd PiS poradził sobie w I fazie walki z koronawirusem. *OKO.press*, 28 April, 2020. Accessed: June 16, 2020. (<https://oko.press/raport-oko-press-jak-rzad-pis-poradzil-sobie-w-i-fazie-walki-z-koronawirusem>).

4 Bram Ieven–Jan Overwijk: We created this beast. The political ecology of COVID-19. *Eurozine*, 23 March, 2020. Accessed: June 16, 2020. (<https://www.eurozine.com/we-created-this-beast/>).

speed of coronavirus spread, it was necessary to control citizens' time, leaving them only with the possibility of passively accepting the disciplinary mechanisms. Imposing new rhythms on society and exercising control over the temporality of individuals and entire social groups is a phenomenon thoroughly discussed in the literature, where social time is approached not only as a phenomenon inextricably related to power (Nowotny 2005) but as nothing less than an instrument of political struggle. (Hutchings 2008) As Valerie Bryson writes, "the ways in which time is used, valued and experienced are neither inevitable nor 'natural'; rather, they reflect and sustain deep-seated patterns of power and inequality. The analysis of time is, therefore, central to the understanding of political processes and outcomes". (Bryson 2016) This kind of approach seems to be justified when reflecting on the pandemic reality, in which many extraordinary procedures of exercising power have effected a change in the experience of time. The current transformations in the ways of experiencing the passage and organization of time, resulting from the outbreak of the pandemic, can be interpreted as consequences of control over the temporality of individuals and society; they also can be considered from the perspective of the microphysics of power (Foucault 1995) and time regimes constituting new strategies of pressure from state authorities. (Pickering 2004; Sabelis 2007)

In Poland, control over the pace of time during the pandemic was exercised at the state level through decisions and edicts resulting, for example, in public institutions and places being closed. The experience of the passage of time was influenced by numerous requirements and prohibitions introduced in the territory of the Republic of Poland by the Council of Ministers: restriction of the freedom of movement, including restrictions of border traffic at specific border crossings⁵, the obligation to undergo compulsory quarantine after crossing the national border⁶, and the prohibition on movement except to meet essential everyday needs⁷. The strategies of pressure applied by the authorities also took the form of administrative penalties imposed, for instance, for leaving one's residence when this meant violating obligatory quarantine or isolation. What helped the new time regimes take control of society was technology – an application called "Home Quarantine" (Pol. *Kwarantanna domowa*) which the police used to keep track of people prohibited from leaving their domiciles. Additionally, the requirement of maintaining a two-metre distance between people, led to a reorganization of public space. The new rules resulted in long queues outside shops and service centers. They remind many people of the famous queues of communist times – the Polish People's Republic. The burdensome memories of the activities of the security services of the former communist bloc considerably influenced how pandemic time was experienced. These pre-1989 echos were also bethought due to goods missing in stores. Although the scale of this phenomenon was totally different, the sight of empty store shelves, no toilet paper, soap, or noodles, provoked such comparisons. For some time during the pandemic, everyday activities such as shopping took much longer than before, also due to "seniors' hours," introduced from March 31 until May 4 2020, during which only people aged over 65 were served. This regulation was also re-introduced after the summer holidays. Maintaining social distance and self-isolation during the pandemic led to a transformation of the space in which people function on a daily basis, which

5 Regulation of the Minister of the Interior and Administration of 13 March 2020 on temporary suspension or limitation of border traffic at specific border crossing points (*Polish Journal of Laws/Dziennik Ustaw*, 2020, item 435) (<https://dziennikustaw.gov.pl/DU/2020/435>)

6 Regulation of the Minister of Health of 20th March 2020 on the declaration of the state of epidemic in the territory of the Republic of Poland (*Polish Journal of Laws/Dziennik Ustaw*, 2020, item 491) (<https://dziennikustaw.gov.pl/DU/2020/491>)

7 Regulation of the Minister of Health of 24 March 2020 amending the regulation on declaring the state of the epidemic in the Republic of Poland (*Polish Journal of Laws/Dziennik Ustaw*, 2020, item 522) (<https://dziennikustaw.gov.pl/DU/2020/522>)

translated into a significant change of their experience of time. On numerous occasions, both in private conversations and in the media, this experience has been compared to a return to the old times under the domination of the USSR⁸. Such a return to the past is suggested, among other sources, by the portal Vice.com, which mentioned Poland among 30 regimes using the coronavirus epidemic to reinforce their power⁹.

In view of the procedures introduced by the authorities during the pandemic, and perceived by individuals as excessively restrictive and oppressive, there were minor acts of rebellion. A visible example was the online protests against the ban on entering forests, which interfered with the anticipation of the familiar time associated with the advent of the new season – spring. This aspect was pointed out by Ewa Bińczyk, a Polish philosopher who popularized the idea of the Anthropocene: “After the introduction of the ban on entering forests and parks, my students wrote to me that they felt they would take to the streets and riot as they were having their spring taken away from them”¹⁰. Despite being open to late capitalism and neoliberal logic, there was no mass rebellion in Poland against the repressive measures applied by the government, because the coronavirus as a political actor seemingly justified the introduction such restrictions. The relatively slow increase in the number of coronavirus infections in Poland during the first wave in spring 2020, compared to Western and Southern Europe, was explained by the quicker decisions to lock the country down and to introduce restrictive requirements and prohibitions. The ability to use state power so effectively to implement the regulations of national quarantine can be explained as stemming from the higher acceptance toward regimes restricting citizens’ liberties in countries formerly behind the iron curtain¹¹. Explained by the need to stop the spread of the pandemic, the need to control citizens’ time was actually accepted by many people, although at first this was an externally imposed attitude. The newly developed temporal imperatives were mostly internalized, which made external pressure no longer necessary. Disciplined individuals began to enforce adherence to the rules of new time regimes on others. An example of this was the social campaign #zostanwdomu (#HealthyAtHome), whose message was repeated on a large scale by individual social media users. Interestingly, it was also used for marketing purposes, for instance by mobile network operators offering new services and promotions. The new time regimes associated with the pandemic were subject to the commodification of time, a process known from analyses concerning the dynamics of late capitalism. (Appadurai 1996, 119; Kopka 2013, 200)

Introducing extraordinary measures of quarantine and isolation for protection against the Coronavirus, the modern strategy of power has accustomed Poles to the fact that the loss of freedom and the related new way of experiencing time is a normal state. Interpreting the COVID-19 pandemic as an Agambenian ‘state of exception’ (Agamben 2005), one becomes aware of the consequences of the extraordinary measures taken by the authorities in suspending the previously familiar temporal order. The Coronavirus created circumstances in which elected

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- 8 Patrycja Wszczeborska: Twierdzą, że Polska cofa się do PRL-u. Przez kolejki pod sklepami i ‘państwo policyjne’. *INN:Poland*, 21 April, 2020. Accessed: May 20, 2020. (<https://innpoland.pl/159087,czy-epidemia-koronawirusa-cofa-polske-do-czasow-prl-u-i-komuny>).
 - 9 David Gilbert: These 30 Regimes Are Using Coronavirus to Repress Their Citizens. *Vice*, 9 April, 2020. Accessed: June 16, 2020. (<https://www.vice.com/en/article/dygbxk/these-30-regimes-are-using-coronavirus-to-repress-their-citizens>).
 - 10 Translation mine. Ewa Bińczyk–Michał Sutowski: Na naszych oczach zatrzymała się hiperkonsumpcyjna gospodarka wzrostu. *Krytyka Polityczna*, 23 April, 2020. Accessed: June 16, 2020. (<https://krytykapolityczna.pl/swiat/michal-sutowski-ewa-binczyk-uwlad-wyobrazni-koronawirus-szansa-wywiad>).
 - 11 Szwedzkie media: Państwa zza żelaznej kurtyny lepiej radzą sobie z epidemią. *Dziennik.pl*, 5 May, 2020. Accessed: June 16, 2020. (<https://wiadomosci.dziennik.pl/swiat/artykuly/7689472,epidemia-koronawirus-covid-19-epidemia-europa.html>).

bodies of state authority gained an unlimited mandate to make decisions about extraordinary actions which transformed the flow of social time. On April 20, 2020, however, the four-stage unfreezing of the economy began, scheduled by Poland's Council of Ministers. The authorities changed the direction and strategy of their actions, and other politically significant actors appeared on the horizon: economics and the economy. The imperative of economic development proved to be so powerful that the majority of measures and regulations were rapidly lifted in Poland. The new set of restrictions, requirements, and prohibitions, subjugating people's bodies and associated with the obligation to stay at home during the pandemic, were loosened. Late capitalism began to demand that people's bodies resume production, distribution, and consumption. Despite the much stronger second wave in Poland, total lockdown was not introduced until December 28, 2020, so that pre-Christmas consumerism was possible.

The impact of new technologies on the experience of time during the pandemic

Due to the coronavirus, an interesting though psychologically difficult situation has arisen. The pandemic has confronted people with civilizational quandaries, i.e. "the main problem is the lack of time, exhaustion, and overstimulation"¹². What greatly influenced the change in the pace of life and the shape of social time during the COVID-19 pandemic is information and communication technologies (ICTs), which, even before the pandemic, constituted an important element in the process of the gradual increase in the pace of life and the appropriation of people's time by the capitalist logic of efficiency and productivity. Changes in the experience of time caused by ICTs are inseparably linked with the development of a new, higher stage of capitalism. (Crary 2013) This process also began in Poland, which was opened to the new socioeconomic model after the fall of the communist regime, blindly allowing its expansion. (Dunn 2004) What was instrumental in repeating the American model was new technologies, which implements the understanding time as per neoliberal values.

Technologies associated with late capitalism are said to have led to the emergence of a new quality of time, breaking with linearity, even before the pandemic. In digital reality, clock time has been replaced by "network" time (Sugarman–Thrift 2017) or "virtual" time. (Urry 2005) In contemporary societies marked by the instant flow of evermore and more quickly consumed information, the time of human life has undergone stratification. It has broken into thousands of elements, resultantly people experience the fragmentation of time into increasingly smaller and smaller pieces. (Eriksen 2001, 47) This new quality of time brought about by ICTs has been referred to using terms such as time–space compression (Harvey 1989, 260–283), multi-temporality (Barker 2011), heterotemporality (Hutchings 2008, 160–176), pointilist time (Bauman 2017, 32), timeless time (Castells 2012), and the extended present. (Nowotny 2005) The continual changeability of late capitalist temporality has become particularly prominent thanks to the pandemic, during which people have begun to experience themselves more strongly through the lens of new technologies.

The spread of COVID-19 led to a decrease in direct interpersonal interactions, aimed at slowing down the spread of the virus. With the lockdown progressing, the Internet became a chance to maintain social relations. Although people's bodies remained in isolation, thanks to means of communication and electronic technologies, isolation was not total. According to

12 Translation mine. Ewa Bińczyk–Michał Sutowski: Na naszych oczach zatrzymała się hiperkonsumpcyjna gospodarka wzrostu. *Krytyka Polityczna*, 23 April, 2020. Accessed: June 16, 2020. (<https://krytykapolityczna.pl/swiat/michal-sutowski-ewa-binczyk-uwiad-wyobrazni-koronawirus-szansa-wywiad>).

the media and digital technologies sociologist, Alek Tarkowski¹³, people faced “a challenge of quickly designing a social world in which relations and social capital are sustained online” (translation mine). The use of technologies became an equivalent of activity from before the pandemic. Internet began to mediate access to services hitherto acquired offline. Despite the closing of schools and universities, school education and higher education were hastily reorganized in the form of online classes. All conferences and meetings, even large ones, began to be held online. Thanks to the wide possibilities offered by new technologies, museums, galleries, and even theaters turned to the Web as well. After closing their offices and sites, various cultural institutions began to organize online events, debates and discussions on literature, virtual exhibitions, curator-guided tours of art galleries, and even film festivals. Online culture took on a new quality, and its development was taken care of, for example, by the National Centre for Culture Poland¹⁴, which launched a subsidy program called “Culture on the Web.” Online video chats also began to replace meetings with friends and relatives, who are now “visited” via electronic devices rather than personally. All these activities have been mediated by remote work applications, such as Zoom, Google Meet, or Microsoft Teams.

During the pandemic, individuals’ previous experience of time shaped by late capitalist logic became even more prominent due to ICTs. Contacts with others maintained by means of computers and phones became even more intensive, and most people spent even more time online than before when staying at home during the pandemic. During the crisis, everyone relied on computer systems, mobile devices, and the Internet more than ever to work, communicate, shop, share and receive information, as well as soften the impact of physical distance, and the sense of loneliness in other ways. Consumers of culture and education who had transitioned to online platforms, began to experience sensory overstimulation and exhaustion by the heightened media noise, including that associated with incessant announcements concerning the advance of the pandemic. Thanks to technologies, time began to flow faster during COVID-19 than before the pandemic. Many people began to experience an increasing level of frustration caused by a shortage of this valuable “resource,” and the consequences of the continual sense of lack of time proved to be immensely oppressive. Technology-mediated experience of time is at variance with the biorhythm of the human organism. (Cifrić 2010; Rifkin 1995, 186) Living in unstructured temporality due to excessive use of ICTs leads to constant fatigue, sensory deprivation, and desynchronization of social rhythms. (Tomlinson 2007; Davis 2013; Virilio 2000; Rosa 2013) During the pandemic, remote education turned out to be an experience too wearisome and irritating for many people. The sudden conversion of education and other areas of life to the online format led to a sudden acceleration of the digital transformation process – the second information revolution with consequences difficult to predict¹⁵. The eminent writer Jacek Dukaj has asserted that “the virus has accelerated us by an average of 10 years”¹⁶. Technology transformed into oppressive instrumentation of power, which – as became particularly evident during the pandemic – shapes the temporality of individuals for efficiency and utility.

13 Alek Tarkowski: Infodemia, praca zdalna i utrzymywanie więzi społecznych. Internet w obliczu pandemii. *Centrum Cyfrowe*, 26 March, 2020. Accessed: May 20, 2020. (<https://centrumcyfrowe.pl/czytelnia/infodemia-praca-zdalna-i-utrzymywanie-wiezi-spoecznych-internet-w-obliczu-pandemii>).

14 Program dotacyjny „Kultura w sieci”. NABÓR WNIOSKÓW. *Narodowe Centrum Kultury*, 4 April, 2020. Accessed: May 20, 2020. (www.nck.pl/dotacje-i-stypendia/dotacje/programy-dotacyjne-nck/kultura-w-sieci/aktualnosci/nabor-wnioskow-2020).

15 Anna Kornbluh: Akademska koronawirusowa doktryna szoku. *Praktyka Teoretyczna*, 1 May, 2020. Accessed: June 16, 2020. (<https://www.praktykateoretyczna.pl/artykuly/akademicka-koronawirusowa-doktryna-szoku>).

16 Translation mine. Jacek Dukaj: Tak wymienia się rdzeń duszy. *Gazeta Wyborcza*, 9 May, 2020. Accessed: June 16, 2020. (www.wyborcza.pl/magazyn/7,124059,25929950,tak-wymienia-sie-rdzen-duszy-nowy-esej-jacka-dukaja.html).

Technology has dispossessed individuals of their time. What seems even more true is the points made by Jonathan Crary (2013), who claims in his book titled *24/7: Late Capitalism and the Ends of Sleep* that the time that should be devoted to biological activities, such as sleep, is replaced by time that is advantageous from the point of view of the capitalist logic of efficiency and productivity. Constantly online during the home-based quarantine, individuals make all areas of their activity totally dependent on technology, cumulatively increasing the pace of the experienced time. The nameless and faceless mechanisms of late capitalism are growing stronger, taking advantage of the crisis situation of the pandemic¹⁷.

According to Tracey Warren (Warren 2003), ICTs contribute to the unequal redistribution of time, causing an increase in social inequalities. For the same reason, the pandemic proved to be a clearly class-related experience because it excluded everyone with limited access to technologies. During the pandemic, some people complained about the chronic lack of time, while others wondered what to do with the excess of time. COVID-19 pushed individuals without digital competence out of the market. Compared to people who had no access to new technologies for economic and social reasons, the upper middle class had a greater chance of adapting to the constant changes in late capitalist reality. The technology-related, pandemic way of experiencing time has led to an increase in social and economic differences in society.

Pandemic time and work

The experimental situation created by COVID-19 revealed how strongly social time depended on the conditions and form of employment, which had already been pointed out by Karl Marx, who claimed that time had a class dimension. The mechanisms linking work and time manifest themselves in individual experiences and differ depending on sex and on the place and type of work. During the pandemic, transformations in the experience of time were the greatest for those who lost their jobs and thus found themselves in an adverse economic situation. Some occupations ceased to exist during the pandemic, while others, such as those of nurses and food suppliers, turned out to be indispensable for the functioning of the whole society, incidentally revealing the uselessness of many of the best-paid jobs, as pointed out by David Graeber (2018), who referred to occupations devoid of social value as “bullshit jobs”. Between these two extremes there are telework and remote work, which have become the most common types of professional experience in the pandemic reality.

Due to the coronavirus, it turned out that many professional activities could be done without leaving home. A growing number of businesses converted their employees’ work into remote work, bringing about a change in the experience of time. In the case of people with appropriate living conditions, the transition from the office to what is called the home office was initially perceived as a chance to reduce the pace of life. The predicted consequences included smaller workload and time saved, for instance, on commuting to the office and business trips. The pandemic was even perceived as a factor restoring control over working time and free time, or over the diurnal rhythm, sleeping hours, and waking hours¹⁸. This situation is excellently captured in the following quotation: “Suddenly the whole world discovered that it was possible to work just a meter away from your bed, wearing pajamas you had spilled

17 Naomi Klein: Koronawirus jest doskonałym kataklizmem dla kapitalizmu kataklizmowego. *Praktyka Teoretyczna*, 1 May, 2020. Accessed: June 16, 2020. (<https://www.praktykateoretyczna.pl/artykuly/naomi-klein-koronawirus-jest-doskonaly-kataklizmem-dla-kapitalizmu-kataklizmowego>).

18 Bram Ieven–Jan Overwijk: We created this beast. The political ecology of COVID-19. *Eurozine*, 23 March, 2020. Accessed: June 16, 2020. (<https://www.eurozine.com/we-created-this-beast/>).

coffee over and washing down your morning dose of cod liver oil, with your hair disheveled from the pillow”¹⁹. It might seem that, thanks to working at home, the former working time regimes collapsed.

The new model of remote work organization developed during the pandemic came to be referred to as zoomism²⁰. It is just as repressive as Taylorism, Fordism, and Toyotism. Previously, workers’ working time and the production system was organized in such a way that every second was used to its maximum potential, which led to an increase in the efficiency of economic production. Capitalist discipline consisted in preventing any “waste of time” and in striving to intensify efforts through maximum pace and efficiency. (Foucault 2008, 154) Zoomism, by contrast, leads to increasing the added value for businesses and entrepreneurs, because the costs of maintaining workplaces (offices) are transferred to the employees. It is the employee who pays for electricity, the Internet, water, and even coffee at the home office. Above all, zoomism concerns the contemporary middle class and the white-collar workers constituting it. It contributes to employees’ self-isolation and weakens their capacity for organizing resistance groups and trade unions, which were very weak in Poland already before the pandemic started²¹. In the context of remote work during the pandemic, when listing various kinds of exploitation by capitalism, Slavoj Žižek adds self-exploiters to the list, citing Byung-Chul Han’s explanation of this term: “Today, everyone is an auto-exploiting labourer in his or her own enterprise. People are now master and slave in one. Even class struggle has transformed into an inner struggle against oneself”. (Žižek 2020, 20)

What has taken place in the new technology-mediated pandemic reality is the erosion of the distinction between private life and working time. Even before the pandemic, remote work was becoming a form increasingly characteristic of late capitalism, leading to the deregulation of norms associated with the division between the professional domain and free time, and making these norms more flexible. (Lazzarato 1996) Remote work is a serious challenge associated with encroachment on the traditional concept of “home” as a private space. (Gądecki–Jewdokimow–Żadkowska 2017) The authors of the book titled *In Work, at Home* write: “To be in work at home is to experience two worlds of meaning and organization within one locale”. (Felstead–Jewson–Walters 2005, 14) The pandemic led to isolation from the previous everyday measures of orientation in time, such as those related to working hours. The individuals who made the transition to the remote work mode began to struggle with previously unknown problems associated with the blurring of borders between two times, each governed by a different logic. Time became loose and imprecise for them. They began to be bothered by a sense of losing control of their time. In order to counteract this disorientation, numerous information sources, newsletters, guides, and instruction videos such as “Lockdown Productivity: Spaceship You”²² have appeared on the Internet. They show what techniques to apply when working in isolation, how to effectively separate working time from leisure time to be able to work efficiently from home, how to cope in this temporality that is not marked by clear-cut borders, and how to navigate amid the blurred contours of the working day and week.

19 Translation mine. Anna Wyrwik: Kwarantanny ciąg dalszy, czyli trudna sztuka nicnierobienia. *Przekrój*, 24 April, 2020. Accessed: May 20, 2020. (<https://przekroj.pl/kultura/kwarantanny-ciag-dalszy-czyli-trudna-sztuka-nicnierobienia-anna-wyrwik>).

20 Adriana Estévez: Zoomism and Discipline for Productive Immobility. *CLT*, 13 May, 2020. Accessed: June 16, 2020. (<https://criticallegalthinking.com/2020/05/13/zoomism-and-discipline-for-productive-immobility/>).

21 Agnieszka Kosiorowska: Witajcie w epoce zoomizmu. *Krytyka Polityczna*, 22 May, 2020. Accessed: May 20, 2020. (<https://krytykapolityczna.pl/gospodarka/witajcie-w-epoce-zoomizmu/>).

22 CGP Grey: Lockdown Productivity: Spaceship You. *YouTube*, 30 April, 2020. Accessed: June 16, 2020. (www.youtube.com/watch?v=snAhsXyO3Ck).

During the pandemic, criticism began to be voiced against techniques linked with self-management in time, which are the skills and practices characteristic of late capitalism, taught as part of numerous training courses and workshops. For example, a graphic titled “Working From Home”²³ shows the illusory nature of these kinds of techniques used in the digital business. Its content draws on one of the most popular time management methods – the Eisenhower Matrix. The Eisenhower Matrix divides tasks into four categories: important, unimportant, urgent, and non-urgent²⁴. In the ironic graphic there are categories related to pandemic reality: “things I have” and “things I don’t have” as well as “things I need” and “things I don’t need”: (1) Wi-Fi, couch, and coffee are things both needed and available; (2) work ethics involving honesty, loyalty, and work engagement is one of the needed but unavailable things; (3) the ability to procrastinate was classified as available but not needed; (4) the last and the most humorous element – pants on – is mentioned as an item that is neither needed nor available. Pants, or rather the lack of pants on, is a memetic element alluding to the culture of working from home and the possibility of creating an illusion of professionalism via a webcam: one does not have to be fully dressed to look professional²⁵.

It might seem that in a time of collective isolation and social distance, remote workers should be less burdened by control. However, several of my interlocutors shared information that their employers introduced new, “pointless” solutions that were meant to be “a kind of substitute” for the old methods of controlling employees’ working time, such as timesheets, keeping track of time spent in the workplace. As monitoring employers’ presence at work became more difficult, employers began to think about ways to keep track of their time during the pandemic-induced lockdowns. One interlocutor Magda, a thirty-year-old librarian, who works under her employer’s supervision, confided:

The management comes up with and imposes pointless tasks. For example, shortly after we switched to the remote work mode, my duty was to make sure that everyone has reported by 7:30 by sending me an email, instead of clocking in at the entrance to the library. The same emails were to be carbon-copied to the management, the director, and the front office. When someone reported by phone, this wouldn’t do: there had to be an email as proof. Then, exactly at 7:35, I sent information to the management on who had reported. I learned to set automatic mailing and I taught others how to do this, so that every day at 7:30 a message was sent from them automatically.

The above example shows how, in the domain of work, technology is used to create new time regimes that discipline individuals. It enables “meticulous control of the operations of the body” and ensures the constant “subjection of its forces”. (Foucault 1995, 137) The aim of these new directives is for paid time to be measured also in the conditions of telework, and to ensure that there is “a time without impurities or defects; a time of good quality, throughout which the body is constantly applied to its exercise”. (Foucault 1995, 151) This kind of working time management mechanisms are associated mainly with capitalism, yet in late capitalism

23 The CLIKK: This is how COVID-19 could change the world of work for good. *World Economic Forum*, 16 April, 2020. Accessed: May 20, 2020. (www.weforum.org/agenda/2020/04/here-s-how-coronavirus-has-changed-the-world-of-work-covid19-adam-grant).

24 In this technique, time is perceived in terms of the oppositions of important vs. unimportant and urgent vs. non-urgent and in terms of gains and losses. Time is treated here as a resource – a precious commodity to be properly managed. This technique is supposed to help people make decisions on what to do with the finite resource of time. According to the rules of the Matrix, one should strive to get more time to do the things that are “important” from the point of view of neoliberal logic, namely those that yield notable gains and bring one closer to success.

25 Praca zdalna. *KOMIXXY.PL*, 7 April, 2020. Accessed: June 16, 2020. (<https://m.komixxy.pl/1500581>).

they acquire a new dimension. In the new model of work, work technology becomes a mediator in the detailed supervision and monitoring of everyday behaviours and in disciplining “«docile» bodies”. (Foucault 1995, 138)

The indeterminacy of pandemic time

Although it appeared to promise a slowdown, pandemic time has led to an even greater acceleration of time. Still, some opponents of capitalism wish to see the global crisis as a chance for a slowdown, a possibility to challenge society’s current late capitalist time regimes. The pandemic has unsealed people’s imagination and opened them to alternatives, creating a space for reflection and debate on the future form of post-work, the limitation of consumption, approach to free time, or the shortening of the working week and the daily working hours. One of the most well-known comments in this vein was John N. Gray’s famous essay in *The New Statesman*²⁶, addressing the common desire to eliminate certain contemporary tendencies associated with the fast pace of time and overproduction. Gray expresses hope for the kind of socioeconomic transformation that would reorient the development of civilization to what is referred to as de-growth. For a moment, the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic seemed to be an opportunity to implement the demand of ecology of time²⁷ about the need to slow down the pace of life and to restore temporal “balance”. (Cifrić 2010; Honoré 2004) The actions undertaken as part of this trend are aimed at achieving greater temporal autonomy and a more natural environment of life in time. In their *Zeitmanifest*, members of the Society for the Deceleration of Time write: “We demand respect for the fundamental temporalities and rhythms of nature. In the name of responsibility for coming generations we must stop our spatial and temporal manipulations of nature so that the natural bases of life in their complex systems might be sustained”. (Matz 2019, 179)

This kind of attitude was particularly clear during the initial phase of the lockdown, when numerous prohibitions created a surrealistic atmosphere of suspension and resulted in the “silence of pandemic time”²⁸. Apart from fear, there appeared a sense of relief, joy at the emergence of free time, and voices expressing hope for a renewal of the world. This positive aspect of COVID-19 was also pointed out in *Le Monde* by Bruno Latour, who commented on the pandemic situation, focusing on the ecological crisis and climate change. On March 25, 2020, he asserted: “For the first time, millions of people imprisoned in their homes are gaining this forgotten luxury: time to think and perceive that which usually causes unnecessary fidgeting. Let us respect this long and unexpected period of fasting”²⁹. The French anthropologist and philosopher thus expressed his hope that, in the newly established system of relations, time would play an important role in shaping the understanding of the negative effects of late capitalism, contemporary economy, and technology, and that it would result in an opposition to the dizzying pace of life in modern societies. Latour’s attitude fits into the narrative about the

26 John Gray: Why this crisis is a turning point in history. *The New Statesman*, 1 April, 2020. Accessed: June 16, 2020. (www.newstatesman.com/international/2020/04/why-crisis-turning-point-history).

27 The authors of *Modernist Time Ecology* write: “Time ecology: this entails recognizing and considering the diverse forms of time – rhythm, time systems, personal time, moments of being, tempo, evolution, and change – in their individual life-forms, as well as in the embodiment of cultural time orders (including the economic order)”. (Matz 2019)

28 Paweł Dąbrowski: Cisza, hałas, sen. *Fundacja Macondo*, 2020. Accessed: June 16, 2020. (<https://macondofundacja.weebly.com/cisza.html>).

29 Translation mine. Bruno Latour: Kryzys zdrowotny to szansa by przygotować się na zmiany klimatyczne. *Praktyka Teoretyczna*, 1 May, 2020. (<https://www.praktykateoretyczna.pl/artykuly/bruno-latour-kryzys-zdrowotny-to-szansa-by-przygotowac-sie-na-zmiany-klimatyczne>).

potential results of the pandemic, such as social reappraisal, an increase in ecological sensitivity, the appreciation of socially important occupations, and the restoration of neighborly care and local activism. Bińczyk offered a similar comment:

In a way, the situation of a standstill, waiting and losing the nearest future, may be salutary, as it stops our hamster treadmill rush and the striving to carry on with the attitude of business as usual [...] The hyper-consumption economy of GDP growth, which must be in constant movement, pushing ahead and rushing no one knows where, though presumably in a wrong direction, at least according to scholars investigating the systems of the Earth, has come to a halt in front of our eyes. We have been given an opportunity to pause, reflect, and challenge the current "common sense"³⁰.

According to the Polish philosopher, the criticism of free market fundamentalism and the ideas of de-growth have ceased to sound utopian³¹. This is because the pandemic-related suspension of the world's seemingly inevitable rules of functioning – its “natural laws,” namely the rules people have come to think of as irreplaceable – revealed their contingent nature, at least for the moment. In March 2020, it turned out that, in just two to three weeks, the “impossible” became possible, and even relatively easy to implement. Societies and economies were hibernated, and the radical lockdown mode was launched. Thanks to the pandemic it became apparent that it was possible to stop the economy for a few weeks. The “business as usual” model was temporarily suspended and consumerism temporarily suppressed. Seeking a potential remedy to the gravest maladies of contemporary capitalism, Bińczyk speaks about the need to create new concepts to name reality. She proposes the term “Eco-verve” (Pol. Ekowerwa), appealing for positive thinking about the future. The philosopher urges the deconstruction of the current “common sense” in thinking about the economy and encourages her readers to challenge the structure of “business as usual” that has upset the balance of the planet³².

Narratives seeking real antidotes to the lamentable condition of late capitalism point to the potential for a more or less thorough systemic change unfolding in the experience of the pandemic. For example, Žižek looks at the coronavirus as a specific opportunity to overcome the pathological phenomena characteristic of contemporary times – discrimination, inequality, and the brutality of the global market dominated by big corporations. He believes that even such terrible events as COVID-19 may have unpredictable positive consequences. These consequences will include the blowing apart of the global capitalist system, on whose ruins a global “new communism” will grow, based on a real alliance of the masses. He writes: “We are not talking here about old-style communism, of course, just about some kind of global organization that can control and regulate the economy, as well as limit the sovereignty of nation-states when needed”. (Žižek 2020)

It is impossible to identify one stable rhythm of pandemic time. There is no doubt, however, that the regulations imposed by the authorities changed the previous familiar rhythms of life and influenced the quality of the experienced time and the pace of its flow. The situation

30 Ewa Bińczyk–Michał Sutowski: Na naszych oczach zatrzymała się hiperkonsumpcyjna gospodarka wzrostu. *Krytyka Polityczna*, 23 April, 2020. Accessed: June 16, 2020. (<https://krytykapolityczna.pl/swiat/michal-sutowski-ewa-binczyk-uwiad-wyobrazni-koronawirus-szansa-wywiad/>)

31 Ewa Bińczyk: Pandemia i rozszerzanie zdrowego rozsądku. Szansa na demontaż “business as usual”? *Biennale Warszawa*, 5 May, 2020. Accessed: June 16, 2020. (<https://biennalewarszawa.pl/pandemia-i-rozszerzanie-zdrowego-rozsadku-szansa-na-demontaz-business-as-usual/>).

32 Fundacja Olgi Tokarczuk (2020): Ex-centrum NR 3. ‘Ekowerwa’ Ewa Bińczyk. Interview by Edwin Bendyk. *Youtube*, October 28, 2020. (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YT6ZJvIBxkE>).

brought about by COVID-19 has shown that the experience of time is strictly related to political decisions, civilizational and technological factors, and the organization of work as well as social and economic life. These experimental conditions highlighted the mechanisms associated with the shaping of time in late capitalism. The coronavirus has helped people understand that so far, in contemporary economy, social time has been shaped mainly with respect to three categories: power, technology, and work, which have undergone serious transformations during the pandemic, thereby changing the social rhythms of life. This relationship was reflected in my interlocutors' observations. The pandemic has made it possible to take a look from a distance at how people work and to perceive more clearly that clock time, associated with the rhythm of work, is not "objective" time, but rather a way of exercising control over individuals' temporality, a pressure strategy that changes depending on the prevailing conditions and mechanisms of power. Thanks to the coronavirus, people have also opened to new technological possibilities, resulting in constant transformations of their temporal reality. Finally, it is worth citing the words of Piotr Borowiec (2013, 12), who believes that "periods of great social and cultural changes lead to [...] changes in the social experience of time," and the opinion expressed by Elżbieta Tarkowska, for whom research on social time is a legitimate way of speaking about upcoming social transformations. (Tarkowska 1999, 343) The observation of time during the pandemic is therefore necessary not only to identify the features of contemporary society, but also to understand the mechanisms of social life and to predict future cultural changes. This means anthropological studies on time can be treated as an element of anticipatory anthropology, a discipline projecting future scenarios by analyzing contemporary events. (Strzelecka 2013, 265)

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